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Unveiling the complexity of monogenetic volcanic fields: a petrological exploration of the Puig Jordà (Garrotxa Volcanic Field, Spain)

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Key words: monogenetic plumbing system; multi-stage ascent; olivine; pyroxene; spinel.

ABSTRACT

The magmas erupted in the Garrotxa Volcanic Field (GVF) in northeastern Spain have been traditionally attributed to direct ascent of magma from its source in the mantle, a theory supported by the frequent presence of mantle xenoliths in some eruptive products. However, recent petrological and geochemical studies of monogenetic eruptions in other volcanic fields have revealed the common existence of shallow magma pockets that are intercepted by new intruding magma before eruption. Consequently, different magma ascent timescales (direct vs. arrested) would have significant implications for the duration of potential pre-eruptive unrest in the GVF and, hence, for the interpretation of monitoring data. Here we report, for the first time, a detailed study of the mineral phases hosted in the magmas from the GVF. We have focused on the Puig Jordà monogenetic eruption (17 ka), located 3.5 km away from the city of Olot, and previously linked with a significant lava flow (Bosc de Tosca). We have conducted volcano-stratigraphic fieldwork followed by an extensive examination of the mineral phases to elucidate the magma plumbing system architecture. The eruptive sequence was characterised by Strombolian activity, with minor sporadic phreatomagmatic phases. The petrological and geochemical analyses of pyroxene, olivine, and spinel have revealed the occurrence of arrested magma intrusions preceding the eruption. Furthermore, our study has revealed that either the Bosc de Tosca lava flow is not sourced from this volcano, or that the eruption involved the emission of two distinct magmas, one of which led to the formation of the pyroclastic deposits, while the other produced the lavas. By comparison with other monogenetic volcanoes from the GVF, the first hypothesis seems more reliable. Thermobarometric modelling of pyroclasts suggests rapid magma ascent from a deep zone at approximately 900-1200 MPa and 1200-1250 °C, followed by the incorporation of previously emplaced magma batches located at 600-900 MPa and 1175 ± 15 °C, and a final stage occurring at shallow crustal levels with lower temperatures (~ 120 MPa and 1110 ± 30 °C). Our results show a complex ascent history in a multi-level plumbing system and have direct implications for the interpretation of future unrest episodes in this, and other, active monogenetic volcanic fields.

INTRODUCTION

Monogenetic volcanism is common in most geodynamic regimes on Earth and is associated with a wide diversity of eruptive styles, ranging from effusive, Hawaiian, Strombolian and violent Strombolian eruptions, to sub-Plinian and even Plinian events (Parfitt, 2004; Kereszturi and Németh, 2012; Németh and Kereszturi, 2015). In monogenetic volcanic fields, eruptive activity is typically characterized by a single continuous, or many discontinuous, short-lived small eruptions fed from one or multiple magma batches within a defined period of time, that generally erupt low volumes of material (0.001–0.1 km³ of dense rock equivalent; DRE) (Vespermann and Schminke, 2000; Németh *et al.*, 2003; Keating *et al.*, 2008; Brenna *et al.*, 2010, 2011; Németh, 2010; Kereszturi and Németh, 2012; McGee *et al.*, 2012; Kereszturi *et al.*, 2014; Albert *et al.*, 2015, 2020; Jankovics *et al.*, 2015; Németh and Kereszturi, 2015; Valentine and Connor, 2015; Smith and Németh, 2017). Although eruptive activity in monogenetic fields is generally less explosive than that of polygenetic volcanoes (Németh, 2010), monogenetic volcanism also presents its own inherent complexities and associated hazards (e.g., Allen and Smith, 1994; Gudmundsson *et al.*, 1999; Pedrazzi *et al.*, 2014a; Alfano *et al.*, 2018; Riggs *et al.*, 2019; Carracedo *et al.*, 2022); for instance, vent location changes for each new eruption. In addition, due to the smaller magma volumes and eruption rate generally associated with monogenetic volcanism, eruptions may be more prone to be affected by external factors such as interactions with groundwater at shallow depth, substrate geology and climatic settings (e.g., Suiting and Schmincke, 2009; Németh, 2010; Kereszturi and Németh, 2012). Individual eruption styles reflect a balance between both internal magma properties and environmental conditions at a given time (Kereszturi and Németh, 2012). Furthermore, while individual volcanoes within monogenetic volcanic fields have geologically short life spans, the fields themselves can remain active for several million years (Németh, 2010; Németh and Kereszturi, 2015). All these factors reduce the predictability of future eruptions in terms of expected location and characteristics.

Monogenetic volcanic fields provide a valuable framework for investigating the relative influence of internal and external factors on the configuration of the plumbing system and the processes driving magma ascent from source to surface. Although petrological studies in monogenetic volcanoes have advanced significantly in recent years (Németh *et al.*, 2003; Petrone, 2010; Brenna *et al.*, 2011, 2018, 2021; Albert *et al.*, 2015, 2020; Jankovics *et al.*, 2015, 2019; Uslular and Gençlioğlu-Kuşcu, 2019; Larrea *et al.*, 2021; Volynets *et al.*, 2023; Didonna *et al.*, 2024; Guo *et al.*, 2024), petrology often remains less explored than physical volcanology in some monogenetic volcanic fields. This gap is particularly evident in the Garrotxa Volcanic Field (GVF), where petrological studies are still limited (e.g. Coy-Yll *et al.*, 1974; Araña *et al.*, 1983; López Ruiz and Rodríguez Badiola, 1985a; Wilson and Downes, 1992; Cebriá *et al.*, 2000; Lustrino, 2000; Enrique and Toribio, 2009a; Gisbert Pinto *et al.*, 2011; Martí *et al.*, 2017). Such gaps are critical, as petrological insights are essential to understanding the dynamics of the plumbing system and assessing the potential characteristics of future eruptions. Stratigraphic analysis is also essential for understanding the evolution and growth of volcanic cones, such as Puig Jordà volcano (located in the GVF), as well as correlating proximal deposits with those found at medium to distal locations. This approach helps to reconstruct the eruption sequence and identify changes in the eruptive behaviour related to external environmental factors, such as the phases influenced by phreatomagmatic interactions.

Another major challenge lies in accurately tracing the origin of lava flows and deposits from unwitnessed eruptions. This complexity might lead to misattributions, resulting in inaccurate assessments of eruption extents and potential hazards (i.e., discrepancies between different geological maps of the same area; e.g. Pallí, 1981 and Losantos *et al.*, 2007). Linked closely to the understanding of eruptive dynamics is the exploration of the origin and composition of the erupted magmas. Unravelling the pre-eruptive magmatic processes is crucial for associating surface manifestations and monitoring data with the underlying geological phenomena and it is, therefore, essential for effective monitoring and risk management (e.g., Albert *et al.*, 2020; Re *et al.*, 2021; Pankhurst *et al.*, 2022; Zanon *et al.*, 2024).

The GVF, which is part of the Catalan Volcanic Zone (CVZ: Fig. 1A), serves as an exemplary case study, encapsulating these challenges within a densely populated region in the northeast of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1B). Unlike La Selva and l'Empordà, the GVF is an active volcanic zone where activity has occurred intermittently since 0.7 Ma, with the most recent event dated at 11.5 -13 ka (Croscat volcano; Fig. 1C) (Martí *et al.*, 2011; Bolós *et al.*, 2014a). Given the likelihood of future eruptions, undertaking volcanological studies to obtain a thorough comprehension of the causes, controls, and mechanisms of volcanic activity in the field is paramount to improving hazard assessment. However, while several notable geological and geophysical studies have been published on the GVF (Gisbert *et al.*, 2009; Martí *et al.*, 2011, 2013; Barde-Cabusson *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Cimarelli *et al.*, 2013; Bolós *et al.*, 2014b, 2014a, 2015; Pedrazzi *et al.*, 2014b, 2016, 2022) detailed petrological and geochemical investigations aimed at characterizing the underlying plumbing system in this volcanic field have not yet been conducted. Contrasting with previous general studies that focused on major and trace element analyses across various eruptions to establish the geodynamic context of magma generation (Araña *et al.*, 1983; López Ruiz and Rodríguez Badiola, 1985b; Martí *et al.*, 1992; Cebriá *et al.*, 2000), in this study we target specific mineralogical signatures that serve as fingerprints of pre-eruptive magmatic processes (direct magma ascent or arrest and potential magma mixing). The magmas emitted in the GVF have been conventionally linked to direct ascent of magma from the source, a hypothesis supported by the frequent presence of mantle xenoliths in some eruptive products (Oliveras and Galán García, 2006, 2007; Galán *et al.*, 2008; Galán and Oliveras, 2014). However, recent petrological and geochemical studies of monogenetic eruptions in other volcanic fields have shown that many of the involved magmas contain multiple populations of crystals, implying the existence of previously emplaced shallow and probably ephemeral magma reservoirs (e.g., Martí *et al.*, 2013; Albert *et al.*, 2015, 2022; Álvarez-Valero *et al.*, 2023) rather than simply direct transport from the mantle to the surface. Interactions and mixing between multiple magma batches prior to eruption is common and may be one of the conditions for the magmas to reach the surface and thus for eruption to occur in some tectonic regimes (Albert *et al.*, 2016). These recent findings suggest that not all the eruptions (past and future) in the GVF might be related to a direct ascent of magma, opening the possibility to other crustal interactions (i.e., magma mixing, assimilation of crustal xenoliths), which has implications in terms of expected characteristics of future eruptions and interpretation of monitoring data. To test this hypothesis, a detailed study of the minerals carried by the magmas is crucial. A comprehensive analysis of crystals from diverse GVF eruptions will reveal variations and commonalities in its magmatic processes. This approach is key to understanding magma ascent mechanisms and will provide insights into factors influencing eruption styles and volumes. The significance of such detailed petrological studies becomes particularly pronounced when considering the potential risk mitigation in areas with very low eruptive recurrence rates since there are not witnessed or monitored eruptions.

To initiate the detailed characterization of the plumbing systems in the GVF and demonstrate the value of a thorough petrological and geochemical approach in addressing the outlined challenges, we have focused on the monogenetic eruption of Puig Jordà within the GVF. This monogenetic volcano is located 3.5 km south of the city of Olot (Fig. 2) and has been previously associated with a large lava flow extending 4 km (Bosc de Tosca lava flow; Losantos *et al.*, 2007; Bolós *et al.*, 2014b); its eruptive dynamics and stratigraphic sequence have not yet been described, and the magmatic processes preceding the eruption are still unknown. The work comprises collection of field data to construct volcano-stratigraphic logs, which are integrated with the sampling of emitted pyroclastic material and lavas (Supplementary Material 1) to support subsequent petrographic, petrological, and geochemical analyses aimed at characterizing the pre-eruptive processes. This study is a further step towards understanding the complexity of monogenetic eruptions in general, and the GVF volcanoes and their potential impacts of future eruptions in particular.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The GVF, situated in the northeast of the Iberian Peninsula, within the Catalan Transversal Range (Roqué *et al.*, 2014), belongs to the Catalan Volcanic Zone (CVZ; Fig. 1A) together with L'Empordà (eruptive activity >12–8 Ma) and La Selva (eruptive activity 7.9–1.7 Ma) (Fig. 1B) volcanic fields (Araña *et al.*, 1983; Martí *et al.*, 1992, 2011). The CVZ is one of the numerous Cenozoic alkaline volcanic provinces, which developed within the extensional geodynamic context of the European Rift System, an intraplate rift structure stretching from the North Sea to the Mediterranean coast of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1A) (Downes, 2001).

Geophysical studies indicate that rifting in the CVZ produced a regionally thinned lithosphere about 60–70 km thick, a crustal thickness of 28 km (Gallart *et al.*, 1984), and a high thermal gradient (Martí *et al.*, 2011).

The GVF covers an area of roughly 600 km² between the cities of Olot and Girona (Fig. 1C), being mostly located in a depression (graben) delimited by two major NW-SE-oriented Neogene normal faults: the Amer Fault to the west and the Llorà Fault to the east (Fig. 1B) (Saula *et al.*, 1994; Martí *et al.*, 2011; Bolós *et al.*, 2015). A set of shallow subordinate fissures running slightly obliquely (NNW-SSE) to the main faults are considered responsible for the ultimate locations of individual eruptive centres through capture of magma during the final pre-eruptive stages of its ascent to the surface (Bolós *et al.*, 2015). The GVF encompasses two geographically distinct zones with different pre-volcanic basement rock characteristics (Fig. 1B). The larger northern sector, which contains the majority of the volcanic edifices, has substrata consisting of Tertiary (Eocene) sedimentary rocks and Quaternary sediments. The southern sector, which contains fewer but larger and more complex volcanic edifices, has a Palaeozoic basement consisting of schist, gneiss, granodiorites and granite (Cimarelli *et al.*, 2013), locally overlain by unconsolidated Quaternary sediments (Martí *et al.*, 2011).

Volcanic activity in the GVF dates from 0.7 Ma to the early Holocene (0.01 Ma) (Bolós *et al.*, 2014b), with eruptive events occurring sporadically at intervals of 10,000–30,000 years (Martí and Planagumà, 2017). Emitted products are leucite basanites, nepheline basanites and alkali olivine basalts (López Ruiz and Rodríguez Badiola, 1985b), which occur in over 50 cones (mainly scoria cones and subordinate cinder cones), tuff rings and maars (Martí *et al.*, 2011; Pedrazzi *et al.*, 2024), as well as in lava flows covering distances of up to 10 km (Roqué *et al.*, 2014; Pedrazzi *et al.*, 2016, 2022, 2024). The volcanic centres in the GVF were constructed during short-lived monogenetic eruptions (Martí *et al.*, 2011) with a total volume of extruded magma in each eruption estimated to be 0.01–0.2 km³ DRE (Bolós *et al.*, 2014b). Most eruptions in the GVF encompassed several phases of activity including effusive lava emission, Strombolian activity, and explosive phreatomagmatic events triggered by the interaction between ascending magma and groundwater in bedrock, sedimentary and volcanic aquifers (Martí *et al.*, 2011; Martí and Planagumà, 2017; Planagumà *et al.*, 2023).

The Puig Jordà volcano (Fig. 2A, B) is located in the northern sector of the GVF, near the Santa Margarida-Croscat- La Pomareda volcanic complex, approximately 3.5 km to the southeast of the city of Olot. The volcanic edifice is a ~58 m high scoria cone with crater and cone mean diameters of 225 and 478 m respectively, a basal area of 0.6 km², a volume of 0.89 · 10⁶ m³ DRE, and a horseshoe-shaped morphology (Fig. 2C) (Cimarelli *et al.*, 2013; Pedrazzi *et al.*, 2024). The estimated age of the volcano is 17 ka (Bolós *et al.*, 2014b and references therein).

A narrow 'a'ā lava flow (Bosc de Tosca lava flow; Fig. 2D) extends from near the northwestern sector of Puig Jordà volcano towards the northwest for about 4 km, reaching the southwestern side of Olot city. While there is no direct field connection between the Bosc de Tosca lava flow and the Puig Jordà pyroclastic deposits (Fig. 2D), they have been associated with the same eruption by previous works (Losantos *et al.*, 2007; Bolós *et al.*, 2014b). This geological mapping suggested that the Bosc de Tosca lava flow was either linked to the Puig Jordà or the Cabriolers eruption.

METHODOLOGY

Volcano-stratigraphy and sample collection

Volcano-stratigraphic analysis and sampling were conducted at six proximal sites within a ~1 km radius surrounding the Puig Jordà volcanic cone (Fig. 2C), based on the volcano-stratigraphic map of Bolós *et al.*

(2014) (Fig. 1C). The volcano-stratigraphic study of the pyroclastic deposits associated with the Puig Jordà eruption was conducted by characterization of deposits constituting the main edifice and located in the surrounding area. Detailed stratigraphic logs (Fig. 2A) were compiled at three representative sites: Outcrop 1, which is an old quarry on the Puig Jordà cone; and Outcrops 2 and 6, which are situated approximately 300 m from the top of the cone, where trenches were excavated to better expose the volcanic sequence (Fig. S1 in Supplementary Material 2).

The volcano-stratigraphic sequence was subdivided into units based on variations in grain size, grading, sorting, bedding structure (stratified vs. poorly stratified), and size and abundance of volcanic bombs. The nomenclature used for bed thickness, grain size and sorting of the pyroclastic deposits follows Sohn and Chough (1989). Classification of primary volcanoclastic deposits follows White and Houghton (2006) and nomenclature for volcanic stratigraphy is based on Martí et al. (2018). Estimates of grain size and sorting (Table S1 in Supplementary Material 2) were conducted partially in the field and complemented with dry-sieving grain-size analysis in the laboratory of samples of pyroclastic material (1 – 4 kg each) collected from individual representative beds (Fig. 3). A morphoscopic analysis of ash was conducted to investigate eruptive mechanisms (Fig. S2 in Supplementary Material 2).

In addition to samples for granulometric analysis, large fragments (20-25 cm in diameter) of volcanic bombs were sampled from Outcrops 1, 2 and 4 (GVF-PJ-1P, GVF-PJ-1Q, GVF-PJ-2C, GVF-PJ-3), for petrological and geochemical analyses (Fig. 3; Supplementary Material 1; Fig. S1 and Table S1 in Supplementary Material 2). Volcanic bombs were preferred to lapilli-sized pyroclasts for this purpose because finer pyroclasts can be more easily recycled from previous eruptive phases; in addition, fine pyroclasts are more susceptible to weathering because of higher surface/volume ratios. Representativity of selected bomb fragments relative to the hosting lapilli deposit was visually assessed. The Bosc de Tosca lava flow was sampled at two locations based on mappings in Losantos et al. (2007) and Bolós et al. (2014) with the aim of verifying its relationship with the Puig Jordà emission centre: a proximal location ca. 1 km NW of the Puig Jordà cone (Outcrop 5; GVF-PJ-4, GVF-PJ-5), and a distal location ca. 4.5 km NW of Puig Jordà, next to the city of Olot (OL-1B; outcrop 7 in Fig. 2D).

Analytical techniques

Sample preparation for whole-rock geochemistry involved rock cutting, cleaning, drying, and crushing (carried out at the Faculty of Earth Sciences of the University of Barcelona; UB), and grinding in a tungsten carbide rings mill (performed at GEO3BCN-CSIC). Areas of evident alteration (e.g., patinas, surface coating, precipitates, discolorations) and xenoliths were discarded during preparation. Seven representative samples (four volcanic bombs: GVF-PJ-1P, GVF-PJ-1Q, GVF-PJ-2C, GVF-PJ-3; three lavas GVF-PJ-4, GVF-PJ-5, OL-1B) were sent to the Peter Hooper Geoanalytical Laboratory of Washington State University (USA) for whole-rock geochemical analysis of major elements and Ni, Cr, V and Zr by X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), trace elements by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), and Loss On Ignition (LOI). Accuracy was determined by calculating the relative error (ER) of international reference samples (AGV-2, BCR-2 and GSP of the USGS) analysed as unknown, and is presented in Supplementary Material 3. The relative error is less than 1.5 % in all major elements and < 4% for most of trace elements.

Thin sections from the seven selected samples were prepared at the Faculty of Earth Sciences of the UB, and petrographic analyses were conducted with an optical petrographic microscope to determine the mineral assemblage and the main textural characteristics of the studied deposits. A detailed study of the mineral chemistry was conducted on the same thin sections using a JEOL JXA 8230 Electron Probe Microanalyser at the Scientific and Technological Centers of the UB. A spot size of 1-3 μm , acceleration voltage of 15 kV and intensity of 15-20 nA were used. Reference minerals were used for equipment calibration (Si: diopside; Al: kyanite; Ti: rutile; Cr: chromite; Fe: Fe_2O_3 ; Mg: periclase; Ni: NiO; Mn: rhodonite; Ca: wollastonite; Na: albite; K: orthoclase; Zn: sphalerite; V: V-metallic) (Supplementary Material 4). In total we performed 236

analyses in olivine, 141 in pyroxene, and 129 in spinel. Data can be found in Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]).

RESULTS

The Puig Jordà volcano-stratigraphic sequence

The volcano-stratigraphic logs of Outcrop 1 ("La Gredera"; 42.14597° N, 2.50641° E, ETRS89), 2 ("Mas Pallau"; 42.14591° N, 2.51103° E, ETRS89) and 6 (42.14500° N, 2.50978° E, ETRS89) are presented in Fig. 3 and complemented by Fig. S1 (in Supplementary Material 2); collected pyroclastic samples are indicated. Proximal deposits (Outcrop 1; Fig. 3 and Fig. S1) show clast-supported, reddish-grey juvenile lapilli-sized scoriae, bombs, and coarse ash beds (Fig. S1a). Parallel bedding with well-sorted 20-40 cm thick layers is predominant, although several chaotic to poorly-bedded and poorly-sorted beds were observed (Fig. S1b, c). In addition, a series of thinner beds (3-5 cm thick) of fine-grained material (coarse volcanic ash) occur sporadically throughout the sequence (Fig. S1d). No stratigraphic discontinuities, erosional surfaces or paleosols could be identified. The sequence is characterised by units with intercalated beds of different grain size, without obvious trends or cyclicity (Fig. S1c), although the uppermost units show better sorted beds with more homogeneous grain size (Table S1 in Supplementary Material 2). Normal grading is not present, and reverse grading is apparent in several of the units.

Scoria clasts throughout the deposits are moderately vesicular, angular to subangular and often show irregular shapes. Phenocrysts of pyroxene can be seen in hand specimens in both lapilli clasts and bombs, with the largest reaching ~5 mm in length. Non-volcanic materials (i.e., lithic fragments and crustal xenoliths) are scarce, although quartz xenoliths of several millimetres in diameter can be found sporadically in the bombs and lapilli fragments (not recognised as independent clasts). There are two populations of volcanic bombs: smaller (64 mm -15 cm) and larger (15 cm - ~1.5 m) types, which have been preliminarily interpreted as fall-out bombs and ballistic bombs, respectively, based on grain size ratio with the hosting pyroclasts. The latter have a dark grey to greenish colour, with varying degrees of vesiculation, scoriaceous cores, and fusiform, elongated shapes. They are often flattened parallel to the bedding, locally forming densely packed agglomerates with welding. This indicates fluidity at the moment of emplacement, resulting in deformation from impact and moulding to the substrate morphology. These larger bombs are dispersed irregularly at all levels of the sequence with no evident grading (Outcrop 1, Fig. 3).

Distal deposits (Outcrops 2 and 6; Fig. 3 and Fig. S1) show a continuous sequence without indication of erosion or paleosols. The deposits consist of well-sorted, angular, medium to coarse, pale grey lapilli beds with scattered bombs (<50 cm). Stratification is largely unapparent apart from the lowermost section, where a change in grain size is visible (coarse ash-fine lapilli beneath the coarse lapilli unit).

Further observations were made in the area surrounding the volcanic cone to establish the presence or absence of volcanoclastic deposits and large-sized (dm-m) bombs potentially related to the activity of Puig Jordà volcano (Fig. S1g-i). Volcanic deposits and bombs of large dimensions were identified in a wide arc around the volcanic cone as far as field observations were made (up to 300 m from the top of the cone) (Fig. 2C). In Outcrop 3 (42.14657° N, 2.51156° E, ETRS89, approximately 80 m to the northeast of Outcrop 2; Fig. S1g) abundant large-sized bombs were identified. Six groups of one to four bombs measuring from ~15 cm to 1.5 m long axis were counted. Outcrop 4 (42.14565° N, 2.50593° E, ETRS89; Fig. S1h), located in a more proximal position approximately 50 m to the southwest of the current Puig Jordà cone base, is rich in large metre-sized ballistic bombs (Fig. 2C).

The Bosc de Tosca lava flow crops out clearly for the first time about 1 km northwest of the Puig Jordà cone (Outcrop 5; 42.15120° N, 2.49492° E, ETRS89; Fig. 2D). At this location, it is characterized by abundant rootless volcanoes (tumuli) and irregular topography, typical of the lava flows in this area of the GVF (Martí and Planagumà, 2017). The lava flow surface consists of a chaotic array of blocks (Fig. S1i), which are traditionally interpreted as brecciated lava. Two of these blocks were sampled for petrological and

geochemical analysis. Finally, the lava flow that might be related to the Puig Jordà eruption according to previous geological mapping (Losantos *et al.*, 2007; Bolós *et al.*, 2014b)) was also sampled in an outcrop next to the city of Olot, about 4.5 km distance from the vent (OL-1B in Fig. 2D) (Outcrop 7; 42.17372° N, 2.46541° E). At this location the lava flow is massive, with a thickness varying between 2 and 5 m.

Whole-rock geochemistry

The results of whole-rock geochemistry are presented in Table 1 and Figs. 4-6. The LOI values are < 2 wt.%, indicating a low level of rock alteration. Samples were classified based on whole-rock geochemistry using a TAS (Total Alkali vs. Silica) variation diagram following Le Maitre *et al.* (1989) (Fig. 4). The samples are classified as basanites with a SiO₂ content ranging from 45.1 to 46.4 wt.%, total alkalis between 5 and 6.1 wt.%, and >10% normative olivine (15 – 18%). The compositions of the Puig Jordà and Bosc de Tosca rocks broadly coincide with the dominant rock compositions in the GVF (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024 and references therein), as seen in the TAS and bivariate diagrams (Figs. 4 and 5). In trace element bivariate plots, the studied samples follow the main GVF trend (Fig. S3 in Supplementary Material 2).

Within our samples, a chemical difference can be observed between the Puig Jordà pyroclastic and Bosc de Tosca lava flow samples, which is more marked in major elements. Overall, the lavas have lower SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃, P₂O₅ content, and higher MgO and K₂O. Regarding trace elements, differences are within analytical error.

Trace element compositions of studied samples are also plotted on spider diagrams normalized to primitive mantle and C1-chondrites in Fig. 6. Trace element data of volcanic deposits throughout the GVF (shaded background) is also shown for comparison, sourced from multiple studies (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024 and references therein). The studied samples mostly plot within the range of GVF rocks. All samples show similar trends characterised by two deep troughs representing negative anomalies of Cs and Pb, with other less pronounced negative anomalies of Th, U, and Sm. A subtle negative anomaly is also observed for Y. Overall, they show a bell-shaped trend and an enrichment in Nb and Ta, indicative of alkaline magmas in an intraplate setting. In the REE diagram, samples show a consistent pattern of LREE enrichment with a smooth decrease towards the HREE, indicative of an enriched source and the absence of significant garnet in the residue. A subtle positive Nd anomaly is also observed in all the analysed samples. The lack of a pronounced Eu anomaly, with an Eu/Eu* ratio close to 1, suggests limited plagioclase involvement during differentiation, and/or oxygen fugacity conditions producing high Eu³⁺/Eu²⁺ ratios. The narrow distribution of the samples within the shaded area in both diagrams points to a relatively homogeneous source and petrogenetic processes with limited differentiation.

Petrographic analysis and mineral phases quantification

Petrographic observation of the pyroclastic and effusive samples revealed different mineralogical characteristics between them (see Fig. 7 and Supplementary Material 6). Under the petrographic microscope the bomb samples (GVF-PJ-1P and GVF-PJ-1Q from Outcrop 1, GVF-PJ-2C from Outcrop 2, GVF-PJ-3 from Outcrop 4) are characterised by vesiculation ranging from 10-15 vol %, except for GVF-PJ-2C where vesicles constitute approximately 45 vol %. Vesicles are <2 mm in diameter, although larger in sample GVF-PJ-2C (<5mm), with spherical, oval and elongated amoeboid morphologies. The solid fraction of the samples is aphanitic, hypocrySTALLINE and porphyritic, with a phenocryst content of <20 vol%, mainly consisting of clinopyroxene and olivine phenocrysts and microphenocrysts. They are immersed in a dark groundmass composed primarily of plagioclase, clinopyroxene, olivine and Fe-Ti oxide microcrysts (Fig. 7A). Clinopyroxene phenocrysts in bombs are predominantly euhedral to subhedral isolated crystals or glomerocrysts ranging between 0.4 and 1.5 mm in size. However, all samples display a larger clinopyroxene population with sizes up to 3 mm. Petrographic observations allow us to identify two different types of

clinopyroxenes that coexist in the studied bombs: (1) beige or pale brown cores to darker brown rims crystals with normal, oscillatory or sector zoning (Fig. 7A), and (2) rounded green cores with zoned pale to dark brown overgrown euhedral rims (Fig. 7B, C). While crystallographic faces can be distinguished in the brown cores, green cores have rounded morphologies. Disequilibrium sieve texture in corroded, partially resorbed clinopyroxenes cores or mantle and rims are frequent in the studied volcanic bombs. Olivine phenocrysts are less abundant than pyroxene. They are commonly subhedral crystals, some with embayment features (Fig. 7D-E), ranging from 0.6 to 1.6 in size and often showing signs of iddingsite alteration. A few olivine phenocrysts are larger (up to 4 mm) and anhedral. Plagioclase crystals are restricted to the groundmass and occur as minute (20 to 30 μm) elongated microcrysts. Fe-Ti oxides mainly occur as tiny euhedral to subhedral isolated crystals in the groundmass but are also present as inclusions in clinopyroxene and olivine, and as isolated crystals. Ultramafic xenoliths are common in the studied volcanic bombs (see optical microscope images in Supplementary Material 6). Their size ranges from 4.5 mm to 8.0 mm and include different mineral assemblages: (1) green clinopyroxene; (2) beige to brown clinopyroxene \pm amphibole \pm olivine \pm Fe-Ti oxides; (3) beige to brown clinopyroxene with mantle and rims in disequilibrium (sieve texture); and (4) beige to brown clinopyroxene \pm olivine, some of them with deformation textures (i.e., olivine with undulant extinction and decreasing grain size).

Lava samples GVF-PJ-4, GVF-PJ-5, OL-1B are poorly vesiculated with vesicles representing only $\sim 5\%$ of the total rock. The solid fraction of the samples is aphanitic, holocrystalline and porphyritic, with a phenocryst content $< 20 \text{ vol}\%$ of the total rock. Phenocrysts are generally smaller than those observed in the bomb samples and consist of olivine and clinopyroxene. The dark groundmass is composed of plagioclase, clinopyroxene, olivine and Fe-Ti oxides microcrysts (Fig. 7F). Olivine phenocrysts and microphenocrysts are more abundant than the clinopyroxene crystals. The olivine phenocrysts are subhedral with sizes below 1.2 mm (Fig. 7G). Rare larger anhedral olivine crystals up to 3 mm are also identified. Clinopyroxene phenocrysts have euhedral and subhedral habits and are generally 0.5 – 1 mm. They occur as individual crystals or forming glomerocrysts (Fig. 7H). Unlike the bomb samples, lavas do not present green clinopyroxene as individual crystals or resorbed cores. They mainly occur as unzoned or zoned pale brown or beige crystals (Fig. 7F). Sieve texture in clinopyroxene is also identified in the lava samples but is less common than in bombs. Plagioclase microlites have lath-like habits with sizes ranging from $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ to 200 μm in lavas GVF-PJ-4 and OL-1B, with more fine-grained sizing in GVF-PJ-5, mostly $< 50 \mu\text{m}$. The laths display swirly trachytic alignment (Fig. 7I). Opaque minerals show bimodal sizing ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m} / 20 \mu\text{m}$) (Fig. 7I). Xenoliths are less abundant in all lavas and occur as quartz and orthopyroxene xenocrysts with a reaction rim presenting a corona texture and as small ultramafic olivine-rich xenoliths up to 2 mm in size (sample GVF-5).

The modal abundance of each phase was computed by the point-counting method (Table 2) and is reported vesicle-free; this was converted to weight per cent using mean mineral densities. Crystal abundance increases from about 14 wt.% in the GVF-1Q sample ($\text{Ol}_{\text{tot}} = 1.6 \text{ wt.}\%$, $\text{Cpx}_{\text{tot}} = 12.2 \text{ wt.}\%$) to about 18 wt.% in GVF-2C ($\text{Ol} = 7.9 \text{ wt.}\%$, $\text{Cpx} = 10.6 \text{ wt.}\%$). Olivine and clinopyroxene abundances expressed here include pheno- and xenocrysts.

Mineral chemistry

Pyroxene

Analyses were primarily carried out on pyroxene phenocrysts, as well as in several pyroxene forming xenoliths. To illustrate compositional variations (described below) of individual phenocrysts, crystal analyses were divided into core, mantle, and rim, and plotted on the pyroxene ternary diagram and TiO_2 (wt.%) vs. En (mol %) bivariate plot (Fig. 8; Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi])). Analysed pyroxene crystals were classified following Morimoto (1988).

The phenocrysts project mainly in the augite and diopside fields with a compositional range of $\text{En}_{31-48}\text{Fs}_{11-20}\text{Wo}_{38-52}$, ($\text{En} = \text{Mg} / (\text{Mg} + \text{FeOt} + \text{Mn} + \text{Ca}) \times 100$; $\text{Fs} = \text{FeOt} + \text{Mn} / (\text{Mg} + \text{FeOt} + \text{Mn} + \text{Ca}) \times 100$; $\text{Wo} =$

$\text{Ca} / (\text{Mg} + \text{FeOt} + \text{Mn} + \text{Ca}) \times 100$ coinciding with pyroxene analysed in other deposits of the GVF (Miranda-Muruzábal et al., 2024 and references therein). The compositions of the analysed pyroxene crystals show a fractional crystallization trend, except for an outlying group of cores with lower En values (circled in diagram) corresponding to the green cores that show dissolution textures (detailed below).

A number of EPMA analyses were also acquired in three xenoliths from Puig Jordà rocks and are included in the classification diagram (yellow circles). The pyroxene analysed in xenoliths present two compositional populations: augite/diopside with compositions in the range of $\text{En}_{34-47}\text{Fs}_{11-15}\text{Wo}_{38-50}$, and enstatite with compositions of $\text{En}_{80-81}\text{Fs}_{11-17}\text{Wo}_{3.9-4}$. The pyroxene in analysed xenoliths from the GVF show a similar pattern, falling into two populations (Miranda-Muruzábal et al., 2024 and references therein).

Mineral chemistry analyses show that zoning in phenocrysts follows several trends. Crystals can be grouped into four types: i) crystals with normal zoning (Mg decrease and Fe increase towards the rim), occasionally displaying stepped zoning (Fig. 9A); ii) more complexly zoned crystals showing sector zoning, including hourglass zoning. Some dissolution can be seen between the sector zoning and the rim in this crystal. The dark and lighter sectors present slightly different compositions, and the outer mantling rim has lower MgO and higher CaO; iii) oscillatory zoning with compositions scattered along the crystallization trend (Fig. 9B); iv) clinopyroxene crystals with green cores showing dissolution textures surrounded by an overgrown rim or by a mantle and a normally zoned outer rim (Fig. 9C). The compositions of these mantles and rims follow the same crystallization trend as the rest of the clinopyroxene crystals.

Olivine

Analyses were primarily carried out on olivine phenocrysts, as well as in several xenolith olivine crystals. In phenocrysts, the core, mantle (when relevant) and rim of each crystal were analysed. Mineral chemistry results are provided in Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]), and illustrated in Fig. 10.

The analysed olivine phenocrysts have a composition ranging from 74 to 87 Fo mol% [$\text{Fo} = 100 \times \text{Mg} / (\text{Mg} + \text{Fe}^{2+})$]. The phenocryst compositions are plotted in the CaO and NiO (wt.%) vs. Fo mol% bivariate diagrams (Fig. 10) differentiating between the core, mantle, and rim, to show their distribution in relation to the crystallization evolution trend.

Olivine phenocrysts are compositionally zoned and two populations have been recognized, which are present in both bombs and lava samples: a dominant group displaying normal zoning (Mg decrease and Fe increase towards the rim) and a less frequent one (~ 20% of analysed crystals) with reverse or complex zoning (Figs. 10). Compositions of normally zoned olivine phenocrysts, with cores ranging from 79.1 to 86.7 Fo mol% and rims from 74 to 85 Fo mol%, depict a compositional trend which can be interpreted as controlled by crystallization. In contrast, cores from reversely or complexly zoned olivine crystals (76 to 81 Fo) do not always plot on this trend but display a departure from the main fractional crystallization trend (Fig. 10).

Several olivine crystals in xenoliths were analysed. While GVF olivine xenoliths (Miranda-Muruzábal et al., 2024 and references therein) have high forsterite values (Fo 88 to 92 mol%), olivine in xenoliths from Puig Jordà and Bosc de Tosca rocks have compositions similar to the olivine phenocrysts, with Fo ranging from 78 to 82 (Fig. 10). The olivine phenocrysts show considerable compositional overlap with analysed olivine phenocrysts from GVF volcanic rocks, except for the lack of mantellic olivine crystals (Fo > 88).

Spinel group

Spinel analyses results can be found in Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]). The structural formula and the partition between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} of the analysed spinel crystals have been calculated according to Ferracutti et al. (2015). Classification is based on the prevalence of Fe^{3+} as the trivalent ion in the structure, thereby categorizing them within the magnetite series of the spinel group. The data are strongly bimodal, with two groups containing i) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 4\text{-}10$ wt.%, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 = 0\text{-}11$ wt.%, $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 19\text{-}45$ wt.%, and Mg# = 9-29 mol%

[Mg# = $100 \times \text{Mg} / (\text{Mg} + \text{Fe}^{2+})$ mol%]; and ii) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 22\text{-}27$ wt.%, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 = 12\text{-}19$ wt.%, $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 45\text{-}51$ wt.%, and Mg# = 40-49 mol%. The range of spinel composition varies depending on whether they appear as inclusions hosted in high- or low-Fo olivine, clinopyroxene, or isolated crystals in the groundmass. Some of the isolated spinel crystals display ilmenite exsolution, probably related to magma ascent and cooling.

The first group (with low Cr_2O_3 and Mg#), includes isolated spinel, and clinopyroxene and low-Fo olivine (<79.5 Fo mol%) hosted crystals (Fig. 11 and Fig. S4 in Supplementary Material 2). The second group (with high Cr_2O_3 and Mg#), comprises spinel crystals hosted in olivine with Fo values between 79.5 and 84 mol%. This corresponds to the main olivine population. Nine exceptions have been identified (red rim in Fig. 11). All of them are hosted in reverse or complexly zoned olivine crystals.

DISCUSSION

Eruptive history

The lack of stratigraphic discontinuities and erosional surfaces within the deposits of the Puig Jordà volcano indicates that the edifice was formed during a single, uninterrupted volcanic episode without any significant pause. Based on the stratigraphic and geological features discussed in this study (Fig. 2 and Fig. S1) and supported by grain-size data (Md Φ and $\sigma\Phi$; Table S1), the eruptive history of Puig Jordà has been interpreted as mainly Strombolian activity producing fall-out deposits and the emission of ballistic bombs that reached distances of, at least, 300 m, together with subordinate dilute PDCs generated by mild phreatomagmatic episodes during the eruption. Magmatic vs phreatomagmatic fragmentation is supported by the textural features of the juvenile fragments including elongated tube-like morphologies and spherical vesicles as well as moderately to well-vesiculation (Fig. S2), which are consistent with magmatic fragmentation (e.g., Cashman and Scheu, 2015). Conversely, fragments from the finer grain size beds appear to be poorly vesiculated and display blocky morphologies with quenching cracks (Fig. S2), indicative of magma-water interaction (Büttner *et al.*, 1999, 2002; Cashman and Scheu, 2015).

The deposits observed at the distal outcrops of the Puig Jordà cone contribute to the interpretation of the volcano's eruptive history. The studied deposits outside of the cone consist of lapilli deposits with typical fallout characteristics, and ballistic bombs of large dimensions (Fig. S1). The similarity of deposits at Outcrops 2 and 6, combined with their proximity, suggests a common origin. Furthermore, their closeness to the Puig Jordà cone (both located approximately 300 m away) and the association of these fall deposits with ballistic bombs observed at similar distances from the cone (Outcrops 3 and 4; Fig. S1) suggest that these materials were generated by the Puig Jordà eruption. Petrological and geochemical analyses (Figs. 5 and 6) reveal similarities among the observed pyroclastic materials, further reinforcing the field-based correlation.

In addition, it has been previously suggested that the Puig Jordà eruption concluded with an effusive phase, believed to be the Bosc de Tosca lava flow (attributed either to the Puig Jordà or the Cabriolers; e.g., Losantos *et al.*, 2007; Bolós *et al.*, 2014b) (Fig. 2D). The geochemical and petrological examination of the proximal samples can be considered representative of the explosive phase of the volcanic activity. However, the origin of the Bosc de Tosca and the distal lava flows is further discussed in the following section.

Relationship between the Bosc de Tosca and distal lava flows with the Puig Jordà volcano

The sites of the lava flows analysed in this study are situated to the northwest of the volcano at 1 km and 4.5 km from the eruptive centre (Fig. 2D). Indeed, the downhill topography of the lava flow path and the morphology of this lava flow suggests the plausibility of its emplacement in this direction (Fig. 2D). Fallout and lava deposits are generally found adjacent to their respective volcanic cone in the GVF. However, geomorphological correlation of the Bosc de Tosca lava flow with the Puig Jordà volcanic cone is hindered by the fact that the proximal zone is covered by the more recent Crosbat volcano lava flow.

In this case, geochemical, petrographic, and petrological analyses provide the best means of identifying a relationship. As demonstrated in the above results, the characteristics of studied pyroclastic and lava flow samples are markedly different. Major element chemistry shows that the magmas that fed the pyroclastic activity of the Puig Jordà volcano and the Bosc de Tosca lava flow likely underwent different magmatic evolution. Higher MgO in lavas with respect to bombs (Fig. 5) correlates with greater presence of olivine phenocrysts observed in petrographic analysis and lower silica content. Furthermore, unlike the bombs, lavas do not present green clinopyroxene crystals.

Therefore, and given that other contemporaneous volcanoes in the GVF show a consanguineous relationship between their pyroclastic materials and lavas, as shown, for example, by geochemical data from the Crosat and Roca Negra volcanic centres (Fig. S5 in Supplementary Material 2) (Coy-Yll *et al.*, 1974; Williams-Thorpe and Thorpe, 1987; Gisbert, 2008; Di Traglia *et al.*, 2009; Enrique and Toribio, 2009b), it seems that the lavas were not emitted by Puig Jordà. However, it is also possible, even if uncommon in this volcanic field, that the Puig Jordà eruption emitted two different magmas, one of which generated the pyroclastic activity, with the other producing the effusive activity. Further studies would be required to confirm the origin of the Bosc de Tosca lava flow, that might be related to the Puig Jordà, the Cabriolers, or even be an eruptive centre itself (e.g., Murcia *et al.*, 2020). Geophysical campaigns to examine substrata underlying volcanic stratigraphy in this zone or isotopic studies might provide a more definitive indication of provenance.

Geothermobarometric calculations

We have considered different approaches for equilibrium thermodynamic calculations to retrieve the original thermobarometric conditions of magma at depth. Equilibrium temperatures were estimated with the thermometers proposed by Zhang *et al.* (2023), Neave and Putirka (2017), Loucks (1996), and Nikolaev *et al.* (2018) by modelling olivine-spinel, clinopyroxene-melt, olivine-clinopyroxene, and spinel-melt, respectively (Fig. 12). Based on the above discussion, we have considered exclusively the pyroclastic samples for the thermobarometric calculations.

A quantitative determination of temperature for olivine phenocryst equilibrium was conducted with the olivine-spinel thermometer (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). We have considered olivine-hosted spinel crystals and the olivine composition (Fo between 80 and 84) next to each of them ($n = 37$). Results indicate temperatures ranging from 1006 to 1266 °C. More specifically, interquartile data between Q1 and Q3 indicate 1102-1186 °C, with a median value at 1152 °C (Fig. 12).

Additionally, we have calculated the temperature and pressure based on the clinopyroxene compositions and the whole-rock (Neave and Putirka, 2017). Melt composition obtained from whole-rock analyses is biased by the accumulation of olivine and clinopyroxene xeno- and antecrysts (as discussed below), and therefore the melt composition is artificially more mafic than the original magma (despite the preparation of samples for bulk-rock analyses; see methodology section). We have considered the composition of the GVF-1Q sample for the clinopyroxene-liquid thermometer, as this sample has the lowest crystal abundance (and the lowest Mg#; $[Mg\# = 100 \times Mg / (Mg + Fe^{2+})]$). This approach is consistent with the fact that despite the higher Mg# of the whole-rock in some samples, the olivine cores have the same Fo content in all the pyroclastic samples confirming that the high Mg/Fe of the whole-rock is related to crystal accumulation. Furthermore, the main olivine population (Fo81-84) is in equilibrium with the GVF-1Q Mg# (Roeder and Emslie, 1970), while cores with Fo>84 are too Mg-rich to have grown from their host magma (proxied by bulk-rock) and thus are antecrysts (Fig. S6 in Supplementary Material 2). For the thermobarometric model, we have only considered clinopyroxene analyses that match the predicted components ($n = 113$), calculated via regression analysis of clinopyroxene-liquid pairs in equilibrium conditions (Putirka, 2008), and we have excluded the green-core analyses. The Mg#* ($Mg\#^*$; $[Mg\#^* = 100 \times Mg / (Mg + Fe_{tot})]$) of the considered clinopyroxene crystals varies from 79 to 84. We have obtained temperatures ranging from 1109-1250 °C, with Q1-Q3 data of 1160-1202 °C

and a median temperature of 1174 °C. The obtained pressures range between 120 and 1190 MPa, with Q1-Q3 values = 630 and 950, and a median pressure of 750 MPa. The main clinopyroxene population, with CaO content above 22 wt.%, corresponds to a temperature of 1140-1190 °C (1165 ± 25 °C) and a pressure of 500 to 900 MPa (Fig. 12). Clinopyroxene crystals depleted in CaO can be correlated to high cooling rates (Mollo *et al.*, 2010) and, according to the calculations, indicate higher temperature (1200-1250 °C) and pressure (900-1190 MPa).

Overlapped temperatures between these two models are comprised between 1160 and 1186 °C, which can be written as 1175 ± 15 °C. The pressure matching this range is 600 to 900 MPa, which corresponds to the Kernel Density Estimation peak.

To retrieve equilibrium temperatures from the olivine-clinopyroxene thermometer (Loucks, 1996) we have considered pairs of crystals in contact ($n = 36$; see Fig. 9D). Our calculations suggest 1049-1171 °C, with Q1-Q3 results comprised between 1079-1141 °C and a median value of 1100 °C. While previous models consider core, mantle and rim, these analyses correspond exclusively to crystal rims, providing lower temperatures (1110 ± 30 °C).

Finally, we have attempted to reproduce the range of spinel compositions with the software SPINMELT-2.0 (Nikolaev *et al.*, 2018), using the GVF-1Q whole-rock composition (as for the clinopyroxene calculations), and we have explored a range of pressure, water content, and fO_2 . The compositions of spinel from Puig Jordà recorded oxidizing conditions with fO_2 between QFM to QFM + 0.5 (QFM = quartz-fayalite-magnetite reaction as oxygen buffer) according to our models at 500-800 MPa and H₂O content = 0.5 wt.%, with temperatures of 1143-1161 °C (QFM) or 1163-1183 °C (QFM+0.5). As a general trend, the spinel inclusions record an oxidizing trend from the high- to the low- Fo hosting group (Albert *et al.*, 2020).

Magma journey from source to surface revealed by mineral records

Based on the discussion regarding the origin of the Bosc de Tosca lava flow, we have considered only the pyroclastic samples that belong to the Puig Jordà volcano for the interpretation of the plumbing system.

The whole-rock geochemistry (major and trace elements) of the studied rocks from the Puig Jordà cone and associated deposits is coincident with the overall composition of volcanic rocks in the GVF, which are typical of basanites of intracontinental extensional settings (e.g., Lustrino and Wilson, 2007). Given this compositional similarity, it is believed that these magmas share a common origin. Based on the occurrence of mantle-derived xenoliths in GVF rocks, the magmas erupted in the GVF are interpreted as deriving directly from the source region in the upper mantle (Cebriá *et al.*, 2000). However, the petrographic and petrological observations (i.e., different crystal populations indicating a variety of thermobarometric conditions) from this study suggest that the Puig Jordà magma underwent a multistage ascent where the ascending dike interacted with crustal magma pockets (Fig. 13) originated from previous failed eruptions (Moran *et al.*, 2011).

As highlighted in the En (mol%) vs. TiO₂ (wt.%) diagram (Fig. 8), the green cores that show dissolution textures plot outside of the crystallization trend of the other phenocrysts, and display En values ranging from 31 to 38. These are interpreted as antecrysts that were resorbed by a new batch of magma. The dissolution textures are explained by a lack of equilibrium between the antecrysts and the new magma into which they were incorporated. These dissolved antecrysts acted as nucleation points for clinopyroxene crystals occurring in equilibrium with the new magma. The overgrown clinopyroxene forming the mantle and outer rim surrounding the resorbed green cores present normal zoning (Fig. 9C).

The other zoning types (normal, oscillatory, sector) observed in the clinopyroxene crystals may be explained by different pre-eruptive magmatic processes. While normal zoning follows a typical crystallization process (rims with more evolved compositions), the occurrence of oscillatory and sector zoning may be suggesting magma interaction between different magma pockets or a multistage magma ascent, causing repeated chemical disequilibrium in the phenocrysts. The presence of olivine crystals with complex or reverse zoning suggests mixing between magmas with similar compositions. Nevertheless, changes in pressure,

temperature, cooling rate, or melt composition are factors which may have contributed to chemical zoning in clinopyroxene. Based on the thermobarometric results and the fact that pyroxene composition strongly reflects changes in the cooling rate (Mollo *et al.*, 2010), it is likely that this is the principal factor for the clinopyroxene fast growth and sector zoning.

A departure from the fractional crystallization trend is displayed in Fig. 10 by a minor group of olivine crystal cores with lower CaO content than the dominant group of normally zoned olivine crystals. The cores of this group of mainly reversely zoned olivine are interpreted as antecrysts which were incorporated from outside the carrying magma. The dissolution textures shown by the cores would have resulted from the antecrysts not being in equilibrium with the new magma. In a similar process to the clinopyroxene crystals, the dissolved cores would have acted as nucleation points upon which new olivine crystal rims grew. It is envisioned that these olivine antecrysts were previously residing in a stagnant magma pocket within the crust when the new magma batch intruded, which would consequently explain their more evolved composition compared to the co-magmatic olivine cores. The same interpretation applies for the more evolved green cores in the clinopyroxene crystals. Disequilibrium between the olivine antecrysts and the magma is also evident in the test for equilibrium curve shown in Fig. S6 (Supplementary Material 2), where these cores plot outside of the optimum equilibrium range due to their higher or lower Fo value (>84 and 76 to 81 mol%, respectively).

Several clinopyroxene crystals found in xenoliths from Puig Jordà rocks plot in the high En field of the En-Wo-Fs pyroxene ternary diagram, indicating a mantle origin. In the case of the olivine, the olivine in xenoliths from other GVF rocks plotted in this study (NiO and CaO vs. Fo graphs) indeed display mantle olivine compositions of Fo 88-92. However, the olivine in xenoliths from the Puig Jordà rocks plot among compositions of the olivine phenocrysts, within the range of Fo 78-82, indicating a likely crustal origin for these xenoliths. Although olivine in xenoliths or single xenocrysts with mantellic signature were not found in the Puig Jordà rocks during this study, this does not rule out their occurrence. While the presence of xenoliths with mineral compositions indicative of a mantle origin suggests a relatively direct ascent of magmas from their zone of origin in the mantle, the presence of antecrysts and xenoliths compatible with crystallization of a basaltic magma at crustal depths indicates that in this zone there may be residual crustal magmatic dikes or magma pockets. Previous ascending dikes might have interacted with these pockets during a prolonged time in order to destabilize the antecrysts and to crystallize mantle and rims of clinopyroxene and olivine around them.

We interpret the results from all the thermobarometric models applied and the petrological observations described above (textures, compositions and zoning patterns), as the result of fast magma ascent from a deep zone (900-1200 MPa) and incorporation of previously emplaced magma batches at 600-900 MPa (Fig. 13). While these older magma pockets display evidence of mixing, the last interaction with a deeper magma leading to eruption seems to be short and/or with a subordinate volume based on the lack of olivine mantle or rims at Fo86-87 (only two rims were found at Fo 86 and two mantles at Fo85). The same applies to clinopyroxene compositions.

Although we have not considered the samples from the Bosc de Tosca lava flow for the geothermobarometric estimations and the reconstruction of the plumbing system, it is important to note that they also exhibit variability in crystal populations and therefore reflect a multi-stage ascent through the crust.

Our results align with previous studies suggesting that monogenetic eruptions may require a series of “failed eruptions” to prepare the crustal column before magmas can reach the surface in some geodynamic contexts (e.g., Albert *et al.*, 2015, 2016, 2022; Shane and Coote, 2018; Coote *et al.*, 2019; Didonna *et al.*, 2024). Such intrusions, though they do not reach the surface initially, are crucial in creating a thermal and rheological pathway for subsequent dikes. Detailed petrological studies, such as the one presented here, are essential for better understanding these processes and improving hazard mitigation strategies.

Additionally, future work in the GVF should include diffusion modelling performed on zoned

minerals to calculate the time scales of the magmatic processes preceding the eruptions. It is possible that the GVF comprises both cases of direct and multistage ascent of magma from the mantle source, implying the possibility of different timings of volcanic unrest. While direct magma transfer from mantle to crust could lead to short seismic unrest and less time for preparation, a multistage ascent would imply different unrest episodes over years, months, or weeks. It is therefore a priority for emergency planning to establish the plumbing system architecture to offer a magma ascent model for the GVF.

CONCLUSIONS

This study consisted of an in-depth research of the Puig Jordà volcano, integrating field-based with geochemical and petrological approaches. Volcano-stratigraphic descriptions and analysis of grain size demonstrate that the Puig Jordà volcanic cone formed from a single eruption which included different styles of activity. The eruptive sequence was primarily characterized by Strombolian activity, sporadically interrupted by phreatomagmatic phases that produced fine-grained beds, interpreted as pyroclastic surge deposits. Furthermore, findings from field work indicate that the Puig Jordà eruption involved the ejection of metre-sized ballistic bombs which reached distances of at least 300 m.

A discrepancy has been observed in the geochemical and petrological characteristics between the Puig Jordà pyroclastic materials and the lavas from the Bosc de Tosca lava flow (previously attributed to the Puig Jordà volcano). One of the most important differences is the higher percentage of olivine in the lava samples. Additionally, the green cores in clinopyroxene crystals were only found in bomb samples, which would further indicate that bombs and lavas possibly belong to different magmas. The reversely zoned olivine cores, however, were found in both bomb and lava samples. This may suggest that processes of magma stagnation due to magmas not reaching the surface, and posterior interaction of new upwelling magmas with older, partly crystallized magma pockets is a common process. The differences between bombs and lavas suggest either that: i) the lava flow does not originate from this volcano; or ii) the eruption emitted two different magmas, one of which generated the pyroclastic deposits, with the other producing the lavas. By comparison with other monogenetic volcanoes from the GVF, the first hypothesis seems more reliable. Nevertheless, future research objectives may include investigating the underlying volcanic stratigraphy at the sites of the lava outcrops to gain additional insights into these deposits, and/or conducting further microanalysis on the mineral phases and isotopic studies.

Typically, monogenetic volcanoes (including those of the GVF) have been associated with direct magma ascent from source to surface, whereby the undifferentiated character displayed by the magmas is interpreted as caused by the absence of significant stagnation within shallow magma chambers/reservoirs (negligible fractional crystallization during ascent) (Araña *et al.*, 1983; López Ruiz and Rodríguez Badiola, 1985b). However, recent studies have noted that stalled magma pockets are common and interaction between magmatic dikes and accumulation pockets does occur. The petrological analyses undertaken as part of this study have allowed an insight into the pre-eruptive magmatic processes. The petrological study shows complex growth patterns and zoning in some clinopyroxene and olivine crystals that indicate the presence of magmatic processes other than normal fractional crystallization, i.e., there is a presence of cores with compositions not in equilibrium with the magma overgrown by mantles or rims which are in equilibrium. These findings suggest the presence of stalled magma intrusions prior to the Puig Jordà eruption and the subsequent incorporation of part of this earlier melt into the final erupted magma. Thermobarometric modelling suggests a fast magma ascent from a deep zone at ca. 900-1200 MPa and 1200-1250 °C (supported by the presence of orthopyroxene xenoliths and the high-cooling rate effect on some clinopyroxene crystals), followed by the incorporation of previously stalled magma pockets (with evidence of magma mixing) at 600-900 MPa and 1175 ± 15 °C, and a final stage at shallow crustal levels and lower temperatures (~120 MPa and 1110 ± 30 °C) (Fig. 13). Our results have direct implications for the interpretation of future unrest episodes in

this, and other, active volcanic fields since time scales of magma ascent might strongly vary based on the magma ascent history.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data underlying this article are available in EarthChem Library, at [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]). Additionally, Supplementary data for this paper are available at Journal of Petrology online, including: (1) IGSN of the samples (Supplementary Material 1); (2) grain size and morphoscopic analysis, additional photographs of the outcrops, and extra plots to support the results (Supplementary Material 2); (3) quality control for whole-rock analyses (Supplementary Material 3); (4) details of analytical EPMA analyses (Supplementary Material 4; see also [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi])); (5) EPMA analyses (Supplementary Material 5; see also [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi])); (6) representative hand specimen and optical microscope photos (Supplementary Material 6).

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1. Regional setting and location of the study area. **A)** Map of the distribution of volcanism of the European Cenozoic rift system (Martí and Bolós, 2019); **B)** Simplified geological map of the Catalan Volcanic Zone and location of the GVF, L'Empordà and La Selva volcanic fields; **C)** Volcano-stratigraphic map and structural elements of the GVF (modified from Bolós *et al.*, 2015).

Fig. 2. **A)** Aerial image of the location of Puig Jordà volcano (Google Earth, 2023) and other volcanic cones. The location of the town of Olot is also indicated. The studied outcrops are indicated with yellow dots; **B)** Photograph of Puig Jordà volcanic cone taken from Outcrop 2 (about 300 m distance from the top of the cone); **C)** Close-up aerial view of the Puig Jordà volcano and immediately surrounding area; the studied outcrops and pyroclastic deposits are indicated; **D)** Schematic map of lava flows near the Puig Jordà volcano according to the Carta Vulcanològica de la Zona Volcànica de la Garrotxa (Losantos *et al.*, 2007); the topographic base is a LiDAR digital elevation model from the Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya-ICGC with a 2 meter pixel size. The Bosc de Tosca lava flow is shown to the northwest of the Puig Jordà volcanic cone, together with the lava flow path towards the river Fluvià.

Fig. 3. Composite stratigraphic column of the deposits of Puig Jordà volcano in Outcrops 1, 2 and 6. Outcrop location is shown in Fig. 2A. Yellow dots represent samples for sieving analysis and red dots are the selected samples for petrology and geochemistry.

Fig. 4. Total alkalis versus silica (TAS) diagram (le Maitre *et al.*, 1989) showing the compositions of the Puig Jordà bombs and Bosc de Tosca lava flow samples. Other eruptive products from the GVF are included for comparison; data obtained from the CatVolc database (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024). Data were normalised to 100% on an anhydrous basis with Fe divided into Fe_2O_3 and FeO following Middlemost (1989). Data in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Bivariate Harker diagrams of major elements plotted against MgO (wt.%) of the Puig Jordà bombs and Bosc de Tosca lava flow samples. Bombs and lavas display compositional differences. Data in Table 1. Whole-rock geochemical data of GVF volcanic deposits is displayed for context (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024).

Fig 6. **A)** Multielemental trace elements diagram normalized to the primitive mantle of McDonough and Sun (1995); **B)** Multielemental REE diagram to C1- Chondrites of McDonough and Sun (1995). The shaded area corresponds to other GVF rocks; data from the CatVolc database (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024).

Fig. 7. Photomicrographs of thin sections under transmitted light. Vesicles were impregnated with blue epoxy resin during thin section preparation. Images **A-E** correspond to bomb samples from the Puig Jordà; images **F-I** are lavas from the Bosc de Tosca. **A)** General image of a bomb sample (plain polarized light, PPL; sample GVF-PJ-3); note the euhedral clinopyroxene (Cpx) and subhedral olivine (Ol) phenocrysts, surrounded by a matrix consisting of plagioclase (Pl) laths, and clinopyroxene and olivine microphenocrysts and microcrysts in a dark groundmass. The largest clinopyroxene crystal shows zoning with a pale brown core and darker brown rim; **B)** and **C)** Clinopyroxene phenocrysts with rounded green cores and overgrown euhedral rims in PPL (PPL, samples GVF-PJ-1P and GVF-PJ-2C, respectively); **D)** Fractured euhedral olivine phenocryst (cross-polarised light, XPL; sample GVF-PJ-1P); **E)** Embayments in olivine phenocryst (XPL, sample GVF-PJ-3); **F)** General image of a lava sample (PPL; sample GVF-PJ-4). Olivine and zoned clinopyroxene phenocrysts and microphenocrysts in a matrix consisting of abundant plagioclase microcrysts and bimodal-sized opaque minerals embedded in a dark brown groundmass; **G)** Subhedral olivine crystals with varying sizes; note the embayments in some of the phenocrysts (PPL; sample GVF-PJ-5); **H)** Glomeroporphyritic texture of clinopyroxene phenocrysts (PPL; sample OL-1B); **I)** General view of lava sample with trachytic texture defined by plagioclase microcrysts; opaque minerals in the matrix are bimodal-sized (PPL; sample OL-1B). Cpx: clinopyroxene; Ol: olivine; Pl: plagioclase.

Fig. 8. **A)** Ternary En-Fs-Wo diagram of analysed pyroxene phenocrysts (Morimoto, 1988) from Puig Jordà and Bosc de Tosca samples, discriminating between co-magmatic crystals (cores, mantles and rims) and

xenoliths; **B**) Enstatite values (En; mol%) vs. TiO₂ (wt.%) diagram depicting the compositions of cores, mantles, and rims of pyroxene phenocrysts and xenocrysts. The red line indicates the group of outlying cores, corresponding to the green cores (see Fig. 9) with dissolution textures interpreted as antecrysts (see main text). Values from GVF rocks and xenoliths are also plotted for comparison (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024). Data in Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]).

Fig 9. Back-scattered electron images. **A**) Clinopyroxene phenocryst in bomb sample from Puig Jordà with stepped normal zoning (composition becoming more evolved towards the rim) (sample GVF-PJ-3); **B**) Clinopyroxene phenocryst in lava flow sample (outcrop 7) with complex concentric oscillatory combined with sector zoning (sample OL-1B); **C**) Clinopyroxene phenocryst in bomb sample (Puig Jordà) with a resorbed green core surrounded by a Mg-richer overgrown mantle and outer rim showing normal zoning (sample GVF-PJ-2C); **D**) Olivine phenocryst in bomb sample (Puig Jordà) with normal zoning intergrown with clinopyroxene phenocrysts and hosting spinel inclusions at the core and rim positions (sample GVF-PJ-3); **E**) Olivine phenocryst in bomb sample (Puig Jordà) with complex zoning including a low Fo core, a high Fo mantle, and a rim with lower Fo content than the core (sample GVF-PJ-5). **F**) Olivine phenocryst in bomb sample (Puig Jordà) with reverse zoning characterised by anhedral core with dissolution texture (rounded) surrounded by a Fo-rich rim (sample GVF-PJ-5).

Fig. 10. **A**) Olivine forsterite (Fo; mol%) content histogram divided by core, mantle, and rim analyses. **B**) Fo (mol%) vs. CaO (wt.%) and Fo (mol%) vs. NiO (wt.%) diagrams depicting the compositions of olivine phenocrysts and xenocrysts. Puig Jordà bombs and Bosc de Tosca lava are differentiated. The location of the punctual analyses is indicated as core, mantle, and rim. Values from GVF rocks and xenoliths are also plotted for comparison (Miranda-Muruzábal *et al.*, 2024). **C**) Reversely zoned crystals have been highlighted with garnet (core), dark pink (mantle), and light pink (rim) colours. Some reverse or complexly zoned cores fall outside the crystallization trend, while their mantles and rims match the other equilibrium compositions (see dashed blue line). Olivine crystals from the xenoliths fall both in the main trend as in the low-Fo core population. Data in Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]).

Fig. 11. **A, B**) Compositional diagrams of spinel crystals hosted in olivine and clinopyroxene, and isolated analyzed in bombs from the Puig Jordà (circle) and lavas from the Bosc de Tosca (diamond). The Fo content of the hosting olivine crystals is represented with a green colour scale. Theoretical spinel from a melt with the GVF-1Q whole-rock composition (H₂O=0.5 wt.%) have been calculated with SpinMelt2 (Nikolaev *et al.*, 2018) considering a pressure range (500 to 800 MPa; blue to red colour scale) and three *f*O₂ buffers (QFM, QFM+0.5 and QFM+1 as triangles, stars and hexagons, respectively). **B**) Two groups can be clearly distinguished (separated by a dashed line). Modelled spinels match the high-Fo group spinels, whether isolated, and low-Fo and clinopyroxene hosted spinels represent different crystallization conditions. Data in Supplementary Material 5 and [https://dx.doi.org/\[doi\]](https://dx.doi.org/[doi]). Olivine crystals reversely or complexly zoned are highlighted (red rim) and follow a different behaviour.

Fig. 12. **A**) Estimated temperature distribution violin plots (combined with box and whiskers) calculated by using three different approaches: 1) olivine-spinel equilibrium (Zhang *et al.*, 2023); 2) olivine-clinopyroxene equilibrium (Loucks, 1996); and 3) clinopyroxene-melt equilibrium (Neave and Putirka, 2017). Violin distributions curves are Kernel Density Estimations (KDEs). Outliers as grey diamonds. **B**) Temperature vs. pressure diagram including histograms and KDEs of results obtained from the clinopyroxene-melt equilibrium model (Neave and Putirka, 2017). The colour scale represents the CaO (wt.%) content of the clinopyroxene crystals. The position of the analyses inside each crystal (core, mantle, rim) is represented by three different sizes (big, medium, small, respectively). Black symbols relate to conditions in equilibrium for the theoretical spinel crystals calculated according to SpinMelt2 (Nikolaev *et al.*, 2018) (see Fig. 11).

Fig. 13. Schematic representation of the multistage ascent of the Puig Jordà magma. The diagram illustrates how the ascending dike interacted with pre-existing stalled magma intrusions (600–900 MPa, 1175 ± 15 °C), which originated from previous failed eruptions. Thermobarometric constraints indicate an initial deep magma source (900–1200 MPa, 1200–1250 °C), evidenced by the presence of low-CaO clinopyroxene and

high-Fo olivine ($Fo > 85$). As the magma ascended, it incorporated portions of the previously emplaced magma pockets, (carrying the main olivine population). The final stage of ascent occurred at shallower crustal levels (~ 120 MPa, 1110 ± 30 °C), with limited interaction between deeper and shallower reservoirs. These findings support the idea that stalled intrusions play a crucial role in preparing the crustal column for monogenetic eruptions.

Table 1. Whole rock major and trace element contents of the analysed samples.

	GVF-PJ-1P	GVF- PJ-1Q	GVF- PJ-2C	GVF- PJ-3	GVF- PJ-4	GVF- PJ-5	OL-1B
	Pyroclast (bomb)				Lava		
<i>wt %</i>							
SiO ₂	45.66	45.12	46.06	45.47	45.31	45.27	45.09
TiO ₂	2.74	2.70	2.69	2.74	2.48	2.59	2.58
Al ₂ O ₃	15.14	14.96	15.25	15.11	15.12	15.11	15.03
FeO tot	10.93	11.86	11.36	11.39	10.80	11.14	11.27
MnO	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
MgO	8.33	8.11	8.20	8.07	9.77	9.26	9.24
CaO	9.78	9.70	9.42	10.12	10.19	9.84	9.82
Na ₂ O	3.55	3.50	3.55	3.73	3.48	3.78	3.76
K ₂ O	2.07	1.41	1.95	2.06	2.22	2.28	2.36
P ₂ O ₅	0.75	0.73	0.69	0.76	0.57	0.68	0.69
LOI	0.48	1.37	0.19	-0.05	-0.39	-0.42	-0.31
Total	99.61	99.63	99.53	99.58	99.71	99.73	99.69
<i>ppm</i>							
Ba	622	627	607	636	663	711	703
Ce	111	112	108	113	92	116	117
Cr*	165	167	173	160	152	140	146
Cs	0.61	0.63	0.56	0.61	0.80	0.84	0.85
Cu	44.8	46.6	37.6	44.2	45.7	44.6	45.6
Dy	5.59	5.60	5.42	5.61	5.13	5.59	5.56
Er	2.60	2.62	2.52	2.59	2.43	2.63	2.65
Eu	2.74	2.74	2.65	2.81	2.43	2.76	2.75
Ga	18.5	18.4	19.2	20.0	18.6	19.0	18.2
Gd	7.42	7.51	7.31	7.56	6.68	7.45	7.50
Hf	5.44	5.44	5.48	5.43	5.39	6.16	6.16
Ho	1.05	1.05	1.01	1.05	0.96	1.04	1.06
La	56.3	56.8	54.6	57.2	46.3	58.2	58.4
Lu	0.31	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.29	0.32	0.32
Nb	69.5	69.3	69.4	69.5	59.9	73.7	73.7
Nd	50.3	50.4	48.4	51.5	43.1	51.6	52.2
Ni*	109	106	110	99	148	145	144
Pb	3.74	3.47	3.31	3.39	4.26	5.02	4.83
Pr	13.3	13.2	12.7	13.4	11.1	13.7	13.8
Rb	47.3	48.3	43.1	46.9	57.0	62.5	61.5
Sc	23.2	23.5	22.0	23.4	26.8	24.9	25.0
Sm	8.99	8.85	8.56	8.94	7.86	9.17	9.05
Sr	906	974	897	977	797	919	921
Ta	4.09	4.07	4.06	4.08	3.54	4.34	4.36
Tb	1.09	1.08	1.03	1.08	0.97	1.07	1.08
Th	5.80	5.77	5.72	5.70	5.06	6.30	6.29
Tm	0.36	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.35	0.37	0.37
U	1.61	1.44	1.48	1.56	1.40	1.74	1.82
V*	253	226	246	258	267	261	262
Y	27.5	27.5	26.8	27.9	25.7	27.6	27.9
Yb	2.10	2.06	2.04	2.08	2.00	2.14	2.18
Zn	98.2	95.2	97.3	95.6	92.0	96.4	95.6
Zr*	239	239	239	236	234	273	276

* XRF

Fig.1

179x213mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.2

172x212mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.3

173x238mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.4

217x177mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.5

138x200mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.6

321x90mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.7

280x205mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.8

197x96mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.9

286x153mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.10

245x240mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.11

253x111mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.12

339x155mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig.13

186x180mm (300 x 300 DPI)